

THE POTENTIAL ROLE OF INTERACTION IN AN ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSROOM

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Djoldasbaeva Khurliman Rashidovna

(Teacher at Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh)

Gulhumar Jumabaeva

(4th year student at Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh)

Abstract: *The article is dedicated to the study of various researchers' viewpoints on the significance of using speaking activities and focuses on different teaching methods to develop students' performance in EFL classrooms.*

Key words: *teaching, CEFR, English as a foreign language, classroom, speaking skills, methodology, communication, vocabulary, grammar, methods.*

The ability to communicate in a target language clearly and efficiently contributes to the success of the learner in educational purposes and systems and success later in every phase of life. Therefore, it is essential that language teachers pay great attention to teaching speaking. Rather than leading students to pure memorization, providing a rich environment where meaningful communication takes place is desired.

Students tend to acquire speaking skills in various ways – for instance, by communicating and listening to others communicate; reflecting and acting; by thinking logically and intuitively; memorizing and discussing. Hence, methods and techniques on teaching speaking skills vary as well. Speaking is "the process of building and sharing meaning through the use of verbal and non-verbal symbols, in a variety of contexts" [Chaney, 1998, p. 13].

Generally, according to CEFR criteria in spoken interaction B1 level students are able to deal with most situations likely to arise whilst travelling in an area where the language is spoken. They are able to enter unprepared into conversation on topics that are familiar, of personal interest or pertinent to everyday life (for example, family, hobbies, works, travel and current events). As for the spoken production, students are able to connect phrases in a simple way in order to describe experiences and events, their dreams, hopes and ambitions. Learners can briefly give reasons and explanations for opinions and plans, as well as narrate a story or relate the plot of a book or film and describe their reactions.

According to an internship report submitted to the department of English and Humanities of Brac university [2009] accomplished by Farhana Nawshin speaking is an important part in learning and teaching second language. Despite its importance, for many years, teaching speaking has been undervalued. English language teachers have continued to teach speaking just as memorization of dialogues. In author's opinion at present time the goal of teaching speaking is to improve learner's communication skill. "Speaking is an interactive process of constructing meaning that involves producing and receiving and processing information" [Brown, 1994; Burns & Joyce, 1997]. It is often spontaneous, open-ended, and evolving. The author mentions that speaking needs that learner not only should know how to produce specific points of language such as grammar, pronunciation, or vocabulary but also those they understand when, why, and in what ways to produce language.

Specifically, the author emphasizes the fact that speaking, as a productive skill, is very complex requiring the simultaneous use of a number of different abilities, which often develop at different rates.

To motivate students in EFL contexts, teachers should include many activities and strategies that attract students' attention and make them interested in the lesson. As Peck [1978], cited in Celce-Murcia [2001], states "Activities need to be child centered and communication should be authentic. This means that children are listening or speaking about something that interests them, for their own reasons, and not merely because a teacher has asked them to" [1978, p.139]. Also, Peck [1978], cited in Celce-Murcia [2001, p.139], outlines some points that the teacher should consider in the activities: a focus on meaning and value, not correctness; a focus on collaboration and social development; the provision of a rich context, and teaching the four skills through a variety of activities. A superior teacher encourages her/his students to speak English as much as possible inside and outside the classroom.

EFL teachers must encourage students to use language for social interaction in the classroom. Brown [1994] advocates that students get enough opportunities to practise the language. This helps them to acquire the language in more natural contexts. Through interaction, students can build their own conversations and create meaning that they understand, and that supports and helps them. Krashen & Terrel [as cited in Lightbown & Spada, 1999] find that communication provides students with opportunities for them to focus on using the language rather than talking and learning the structure of the language. Therefore, the topics or themes around which students learn language should capture their attention and

encourage them to interact more with each other. Teachers' emphasis should be on making meaning, not on error correction.

About the strategies the teacher should focus on, the author puts the emphasis on the fact that they should be interesting and should capture students' attention. In the young learners' classroom, these activities are usually centred on songs, poems, chants, drama, stories, games and Total Physical Response (TPR) activities. All these activities can affect young learners and enhance their learning the language. Deesri [2002] believes that many teachers consider games as merely fun activities that are a waste of time, but he states that games in the EFL context are much more than that. He believes that games include many factors such as rules, competition, relaxation, and learning which are all useful in promoting speaking. Games are useful because they offer situations that lower students' stress and give students chances to engage in real communication. It is asserted that students are encouraged when they have friendly competition with each other, so each student will participate in the classroom. Consequently, teachers can use these games to present and review new knowledge, vocabulary, and grammar. Games are good teaching tools that can be used to develop students' language learning and practise communication.

Teachers should take into consideration that songs can develop language skills, and bring enjoyment and fun into the classroom. As Schoepp [2001, Para. 8] suggests "The enjoyment aspect of learning language through songs is directly related to affective factors." The affective filter is one of the five hypotheses that Krashen presents. Krashen [as cited in Schoepp, 2001, Para. 6] explains that for optimal learning to occur the affective filter must be weak. A weak filter means that a positive attitude towards learning is present. Schoepp [2001, Para. 6] adds that songs are one of the methods that achieve a weak affective filter and promote language learning, and can be used to present a topic; practice language; stimulate discussion of attitude and feelings; provide a comfortable atmosphere and bring variety and fun to learning.

In addition, using puppets helps students to interact with each other. As Gronna, Serna, Kennedy and Prater [1999, Para.1] believe, puppets can be used to teach the language functions and the social skills of greeting, responding to conversation, and initiating conversation. Using puppets in the classroom is one of the ways to encourage students to learn English. Ozdeniz [2000, Para. 9] has stated that "Puppets can encourage your students to experiment more with the language and "have a go" when they may have otherwise remained silent." In EFL classrooms students are not comfortable and feel hesitant to speak English because

they are not sure of the words. So as Ozdeniz [2000, Para. 9] states, "when a child speaks through the puppet, it is not the child who is perceived as making errors but the puppet, and children find this liberating."

The strategies the teacher uses can be fun and enjoyable, and at the same time achieve academic goals. Teachers should choose activities that enhance students learning, and avoid ones that are a waste of teachers' and students' time. Good & Brophy [2000, p. 30] state that "learning should be fun and motivation problems appear because the teacher somehow has converted an inherently enjoyable activity into drudgery." It can therefore be concluded that interesting and fun strategies can be used to promote speaking in the EFL classroom. According to Brown [1994], if strategies are intrinsically motivating and appeal to students' goals and interests then it can have a positive impact on their speaking.

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